

Contextualizing curriculum and mother/home language in the early grades in Balochistan

Palwasha Badar Jalalzai
Educationist, Education Program Manager
Ulasyar Jalalzai
Capacity Building Expert

ABSTRACT: Balochistan, a geopolitically significant province in Pakistan, faces profound educational challenges exacerbated by its unique socio-political and ethnic landscape. Despite its strategic importance and vast natural resources, the region suffers from low human development indicators, influenced by ongoing insurgencies, international interference, and a significant refugee influx. The educational sector, particularly in early grades, reflects this stagnation, with curriculum and language policies that do not cater to the region's ethnolinguistic diversity. This paper investigates the impact of these policies on educational outcomes in Balochistan, where the imposition of Urdu and an irrelevant curriculum undermine effective learning. Drawing on Culturally Relevant Pedagogy (CRP), it argues for a curriculum that acknowledges and incorporates the cultural and linguistic realities of Balochistan. The research underscores the importance of mother/home language instruction in early grades, advocating for a curriculum that reflects the daily lives and experiences of the students. The analysis highlights how current practices contribute to ethnic disharmony and poor learning outcomes, proposing a shift towards a more inclusive and contextually appropriate educational framework to foster better educational achievements and social cohesion in the province.

Keywords: Culturally Relevant Pedagogy, Mother/Home Language Instruction, Curriculum Contextualization, Educational Outcomes in Balochistan

Introduction
Background and Context
Literature Review
Successful Initiatives and Case Studies
Recommendations
Challenges and Opportunities
Conclusions
References

1. Introduction

Balochistan, sharing its territorial boundaries with Iran and Afghanistan, perennially garners attention due to its substantial geostrategic significance, the continual influx and harboring of Afghan refugees, along with the active presence of numerous militant factions such as Tehreek e Taliban Pakistan, ISIS, Sectarian groups, and the ongoing Baloch insurgent movement (Samad, 2014; Ahmad 2015). Despite its astonishingly low population density, Balochistan's expansive landmass of over 347.19 square kilometers could easily accommodate several European countries within its borders. The province has over 700 kilometers of coastline, and the Chinese-developed Gwadar seaport is a notable feature. The terrain of Balochistan is comprised of vast desert expanses in the Center-west,

expansive lowlands in the north-east, and rugged mountainous landscapes in the north. Its ethnic tapestry is a direct reflection of its geographical diversity. Ethnically, the region is a melting pot, with the Baloch and Pashtun communities constituting the majority, and other ethnic groups such as the Hazaras and Sindhis, among others, contributing to the region's diverse cultural mosaic (Government of Balochistan, n.d.).

Since the Russian invasion of Afghanistan in 1979, Balochistan has been engulfed in a whirlwind of external and internal adversities, including an unprecedented influx and unsanctioned naturalization of refugees, escalating ethnic strife, the persistent Baloch insurgency, and palpable international interference. This region has metamorphosed into a strategic theatre for various international forces over the years (Khan & Ahmed, 2022). One might assume that the vested interests of global superpowers such as the United States and China would drive support for local economic development initiatives. However, this hypothesis stands in striking contrast to the truth. Indicators of human development in Balochistan portray a bleak picture, with a discernible downward trend over the past two decades (Ramsey, 2017).

Two pivotal moments in recent history had the potential to steer Balochistan onto a path of development: first, the post-Zia era, and second, the period following the 18th constitutional amendment. Pakistan's sociocultural and developmental history, particularly in Balochistan, can be clearly divided into pre- and post-Zia eras. Zia-ul-Haq implemented stringent Islamic laws to foster a more fundamentalist society amenable to supporting the Afghan war against the Russian invasion. He introduced radical Islamic ideologies and substantially altered the educational curriculum by incorporating an artificial national identity that ignored the nation's multiethnic fabric (Syed, Saeed, & Martin, 2015).

In 2010, under the democratic political governance of Asif Ali Zardari, provincial autonomy coupled with fiscal independence was granted for the first time, decentralizing pivotal sectors such as education and health to the provinces. This transition endowed provinces with the authority to legislate and formulate policies tailored to their respective contexts. However, the anticipated positive outcome appeared to diverge significantly from reality, as elucidated by the findings of Jamal and Iqbal (2021) in their study, "Educational Status of Pakistan: Pre and Post 18th Amendment Scenario." The researchers concluded that the amelioration in educational status across the provinces has not been remarkable, with the notably underwhelming performance in Sindh, the country's second-largest province, emerging as a serious concern (Jamal & Iqbal, 2021).

Upon scrutinizing the education sector, particularly in the realm of learning, it becomes apparent that Balochistan significantly trails behind. This lag can be attributed to two main factors. Firstly, the infusion of stringent and radical Islamic notions into the curriculum, accompanied by the imposition of the Urdu language to foster a national identity, has had a marked impact (Ahmad, 2004; Mehfooz, 2021). Secondly, the chronic neglect of Balochistan since the inception of Pakistan has stymied the province's ability to develop its own intellectual capacities (Education Sector Analysis Report, Government of Balochistan, 2020). Although the province has been granted the autonomy to tailor or adapt the curriculum to its unique context, there has been a conspicuous absence of progress in

this regard (Education Sector Analysis Report, Government of Balochistan, 2020). The ramifications of this stagnation are most profoundly felt by the children of Balochistan, who, upon navigating through the educational system, emerge with a conspicuous void in acquired learning (Education Sector Analysis Report, Government of Balochistan, 2020).

The educational milieu in Balochistan exhibits inadequacies in learning outcomes. In 2013, a study conducted by the Pakistan Reading Project (PRP) under the sponsorship of the United States Agency for International Development (USAID) revealed that 42% of the province's children are unable to read in Urdu, a stark contrast to the national average of 22% (Pakistan Reading Program, 2013). Concurrently, the Annual Status of Education Report (ASER) of 2018 highlighted Balochistan's deteriorating proficiency across a spectrum of tested skills, with only 28.3% of third-grade students able to read a sentence in Urdu (ASER Pakistan, 2018). This proficiency marginally improves to 40% by the fifth grade. The English language learning indicators are even more disquieting, with fundamental reading skills, earmarked for first-grade competency, essentially unmet in both third and fifth-grade assessments.

Globally, education serves as a conduit for promoting peace, cooperation, and local potential development (Hantzopoulos, 2011). However, the province lacks the capacity and initiative to leverage education for human capital development, ethnic harmony, and multiethnic identity recognition, all of which are critical for transitioning from radicalization to peaceful, harmonic cohabitation. As a result, imposing a foreign language for instruction results in poor learning outcomes (Trudell & Piper, 2014). In a bilingual context, the significance of the mother/home language on a child's social, personal, and educational development is profound, impacting second-language acquisition (Yazici, Ilter, & Glover, 2010; Seid, 2016).

Language obstacles are the most common learning impediment in Balochistan, as Urdu, the official language, is unfamiliar to most students in the region, making comprehension difficult (Imran, 2018). The major languages spoken in Balochistan include Balochi, Brahvi, Pashto, Hazargi, Dari and Sindhi. This problem extends to English, which was introduced alongside Urdu in the first grade or Kachi. A study on the 1994 Ethiopian education reform, which allowed governments to choose the language of instruction in primary schools, found that using the mother/home language for instruction improved educational achievements (Seid, 2016).

This paper is aimed at examining how the learning levels could be improved through contextualizing the curriculum to the realities of the province and using the mother/home language in early grades. Culturally Relevant Pedagogy (CRP), developed by Gloria Ladson-Billings, is a holistic educational framework. It prioritizes cultural identity and academic growth, aiming to empower students to maintain their cultural heritage while becoming culturally competent and socially conscious (Ladson-Billings, n.d.). Contextualizing the curriculum in this paper means aligning it with the specific context and unique characteristics of Balochistan. This means that the curriculum content should be historically, culturally, and situationally relevant, directly reflecting the daily lives of the students and the livelihoods of their families. In essence, it should resonate with the realities

and experiences of the children and their communities in Balochistan. While using Ladson-Billings' CRP framework, pedagogy shall follow and connect to the contextualized curriculum.

The problem lies in the curriculum that does not respond to the requirements of the province and that forced use of Urdu, which is not even spoken by 1% of the population in Balochistan (Bureau of statistics, 2017). It has further created disharmony and ethnic divide, as it does not recognize the ethnic identities in Balochistan. An important example is the subject of social studies, with history glorifying the Arab Islamic heroes and significant figures of the Indian Sub-continent but negligent or no mention of any of the local heroes (Ahmad, 2004). The same goes for the mention of animals, fruits, and vegetables that are not local to Balochistan, and therefore, children cannot make the connection, resulting in rote memorization without understanding, especially when all of this is taught in a language they do not understand.

Education has long been recognized as an important factor in both peacebuilding and conflict resolution, but in Balochistan, children's sense of belonging is completely ignored without any attention paid to cultivating ideas of mutual cohabitation in harmony and peace (Nishanthi, 2020). The education system and, specifically, the curriculum completely ignore the natural endowments of children before they enter school, particularly the use of the mother/home language. On day one, a child is introduced to Urdu, and exactly at this point, every child in Balochistan is put at an immense disadvantage in learning (Asif, Afzal, & Bashir, 2020). Further, Qasim and Qasim (2014) in their analytical review of Pakistan's education policy emphasize that teaching in the mother/home language for primary education can be successfully implemented, minimizing dropout levels and aiding children in their educational careers (Qasim & Qasim, 2014).

2. Background and Context

The education system in Balochistan grapples with a myriad of challenges closely intertwined with the broader issues of language instruction and the development of contextualized curriculum. An essential aspect to consider is the capacity of the Bureau of Curriculum and Extension (BCE) to create a curriculum tailored to the province's unique student population. According to the Balochistan Education Sector Plan (BESP) 2020-2025, the BCE faces significant limitations in curriculum development, which is pivotal to addressing the region's educational crisis (Government of Balochistan, 2020). The BCE often lacks the necessary technical expertise, resources, and political support required to design a curriculum that effectively addresses the specific needs of Balochistan's students.

The implementation of the Single National Curriculum (SNC) in Balochistan raises serious concerns due to its lack of contextualization for the province's diverse requirements. The SNC's inability to address the prevalent multigrade teaching situations found in over fifty percent of Balochistan's schools (EMIS Balochistan – 2021-2022) exacerbates the learning crisis. Given the prevalence of small schools, multigrade teaching necessitates a curriculum that considers linguistic diversity and sociocultural factors. However, the Bureau

of Curriculum and Extension (BCE) faces limitations in its efforts to develop such a curriculum.

The introduction of the SNC in Pakistan, aimed at standardizing education, overlooks Balochistan's multigrade teaching context, exacerbating the region's learning challenges. Additionally, the SNC places primary emphasis on instruction in Urdu and English, disadvantaging students who do not speak these languages at home, leading to limited learning, alienation, high dropout rates, and grade repetition. Balochistan's unique educational environment demands a more customized approach to curriculum development.

The BESP 2020-2025 recognizes teacher training and professional development as pivotal factors in addressing the province's education challenges (Government of Balochistan, 2020). A proficient and well-trained teaching force is essential for the successful implementation of mother tongue instruction and a contextualized curriculum. However, the current pre-service and in-service teacher training programs in Balochistan do not adequately prepare teachers for the complexities of teaching in multilingual and multicultural classrooms. Addressing this issue requires improved teacher recruitment policies, comprehensive teacher training programs, and ongoing professional development to equip teachers for effective instruction in linguistically diverse classrooms.

Furthermore, the BESP 2020-2025 underscores the importance of community participation in the development and implementation of education policies (Government of Balochistan, 2020). Involving local communities in curriculum development and language policy formation can ensure that the needs of Balochistan's diverse population are adequately addressed. However, the current education system falls short in effectively engaging communities in these processes, resulting in a lack of ownership and support for education initiatives.

The Balochistan Education Sector Plan (2020-2025) acknowledges the significance of mother/home language instruction and contextualized curriculum in addressing the learning crisis in the region. The plan proposes several strategies to overcome these challenges and enhance the BCE's ability to create a curriculum tailored to the local context.

- Formulation and execution of a comprehensive language policy recognizing the importance of native language instruction in early education and ensuring curriculum relevance to the local context.
- Enhancement of teachers' capacity to deliver education in the native language through pre-service and in-service training, coupled with continuous support.
- Collaboration with local communities and relevant stakeholders to develop and advance educational resources using the native language as a medium of instruction.
- Assurance of culturally and linguistically appropriate assessments to accurately gauge student progress and support evidence-based decision-making.

- Strengthening the BCE's institutional capacity through targeted investments in human resources, infrastructure, and technology, fostering a culture of evidence-based decision-making and continuous improvement.
- Establishment of partnerships with local and international experts, organizations, and academic institutions to provide technical assistance and support for curriculum development, implementation, and evaluation.
- Advocacy for increased political support and commitment to prioritize tailored curriculum development for Balochistan's students, including securing sufficient funding and resources for the Balochistan Curriculum and Textbook Board (BCE).

The Balochistan Education Sector Plan (2020-2025) presents a comprehensive strategy for addressing the issues related to mother tongue education and tailored curriculum in the region. Through the implementation of these proposed strategies, the educational system in Balochistan can strive towards improving academic achievements for all students, irrespective of their cultural and linguistic diversities.

Scope

This paper explores the multiple obstacles and opportunities in the field of student learning in Balochistan, with a focus on the use of mother/home language in early grades and the development of contextualized curriculum. Balochistan is characterized by sociopolitical difficulties, ethnic diversity, and linguistic complications. The present literature analysis gives crucial insights into the importance of curriculum contextualization and mother/home language instruction, establishing the need for a thorough examination of these subjects in the context of Balochistan.

The content of this paper is based on current literature, academic research in relevant contexts, and an examination of present curriculum design and language policies in Balochistan's educational landscape. Given the limited research conducted within the specific context of Balochistan, this study draws extensively from research conducted in analogous settings that are germane to the subject matter. This province, distinguished by its linguistic diversity and numerous ethnic groups, provides an excellent case study for examining the consequences of mother-tongue instruction and contextualized curriculum in a linguistically rich yet educationally challenged environment. The paper is based on successful instances and pilots in the province and country, and it investigates how learning materials and instructional communication in mother/home language might favorably affect their learning. It starts a discussion about delving into this topic and gives policymakers and legislators food for thought about focusing on mother/home language as a means of reaching learning objectives for children while cultivating a sense of peaceful co-existence.

3. Literature Review

The literature on curriculum contextualization and mother/home language promotion in early grades is vast, spanning a range of language policies, curricula, and teaching practices. Balochistan is an information-poor province, especially in terms of availability and generation of empirical evidence (BESP 2021-2025). Literature selection for review of the

topic under examination thus became difficult due to the dearth of research in the province. Contextually relevant literature was identified to be included. The literature review aims to synthesize the key findings and debates in this area, focusing on the implications for the educational context in Balochistan.

By analyzing successful initiatives, case studies, and recommendations, this study aims to determine how contextualized curriculum and instruction in students' mother/home languages can increase access to quality education for the most disadvantaged children in Balochistan while also fostering social cohesion and peace (Benson & Kosonen, 2013; Collier, 2014; Hamid et al., 2010). The Balochistan Introduction of Mother/home Languages as Compulsory Additional Subject at Primary Level Act, 2014, and its influence on the province's future education policy and practice will also be discussed.

Importance of Mother/home Language Instruction in Early Grades

Several studies have argued that the use of mother/home languages as instructional mediums and learning materials, particularly in early childhood education, is essential for cognitive development and improved academic performance (Ball, 2011; Cummins, 2000; Thomas & Collier, 2002). Research in Ethiopia, contextually similar to Balochistan, suggests that learning first in the mother/home language (in grades) improves mathematics test scores later (in grade 5) by 0.159 standard deviations, suggesting students taught first in their mother/home language learn in English better after they switch to English-instruction classrooms (Seid, Y., 2018).

This evidence supports the argument that mother/home language instruction improves educational outcomes in primary school. Children who were able to learn in their mother/home languages performed significantly better academically, were less likely to fail out of school, and had higher self-esteem. Another study exploring the multilingual benefit in relation to language learning and mathematical learning finds a positive role of mother/home language literacy in language learning as well as mathematical learning (Dahm, R., & Angelis, G., 2018).

In contrast, children who are not taught in their mother/home language frequently struggle with cognitive and linguistic issues, resulting in poor academic performance and higher dropout rates (Heugh, 2011; RTI International, 2016).

Contextualizing Curriculum and Pedagogical Practices

In the realm of investigating pedagogical approaches, Sigthorsson (2008) underscored the significance of educators' expertise, with a specific focus on their familiarity with subject matter, language employed for instruction, and availability of instructional materials within the classroom setting. In a study conducted by Sargent (2010), the author explored the effects of national curriculum reform on classroom interaction within rural primary schools. The research focused on examining the influence of new curriculum materials on teaching methods and the subsequent emphasis placed on learners' self-expression and thinking abilities. The findings of the study indicated that the implementation of the revised curriculum resulted in notable changes in instructional approaches employed

by teachers. Specifically, there was a discernible shift towards prioritizing learners' self-expression and fostering their critical thinking skills. In a study conducted by Mohd Meerah et al. (2010), it was observed that teachers working in educational institutions catering to socially disadvantaged rural children in Malaysia exhibited a preference for conventional teacher-centered instructional approaches while displaying reluctance towards the adoption of inquiry-based teaching methods. In a study conducted by Peat (2009), it was observed that teachers in rural schools in South Africa encountered difficulties in effectively implementing creative teaching strategies. Similarly, Eloff, Louw, and Wium (2010) conducted research and found that both rural and urban settings presented challenges in providing support to foundation phase teachers in terms of enhancing their literacy and numeracy skills. The collective findings of this study indicate a clear inclination towards traditional teaching methods and highlight the difficulties encountered when attempting to incorporate more innovative approaches. These findings shed light on the existing disparity between current teaching practices and the desired educational objectives as culturally responsive pedagogy for teacher education prepares teachers to be sensitive to the cultures of their students and to use their understandings about how culture influences their learning in their day-to-day planning for teaching students (Stoicovy, C. 2002).

Customized curricula and pedagogical techniques are critical for guaranteeing the relevance, engagement, and efficacy of education for diverse learners (Smith, 2020; Johnson & Martinez, 2021). (Castagno & Brayboy, 2008; Demmert & Towner, 2003; McCarty, 2002).

Language Policy and Its Implications for Education

Language policy plays a significant role in shaping educational opportunities and outcomes, particularly in multilingual contexts such as Balochistan (Skutnabb-Kangas, 2000; Tollefson, 2008). In many countries, language policies have historically favored dominant or colonial languages, marginalizing minority languages and their speakers (Rassool, 2007; Skutnabb-Kangas & Phillipson, 2017). These policies can have profound consequences for education, as students who do not speak the language of instruction often struggle academically (Heugh, 2011; RTI International, 2016).

In Pakistan, the language policy has been heavily influenced by the country's colonial history, with English and Urdu being prioritized over indigenous languages (Rahman, 2002). This policy has had significant implications for Balochistan, where most students do not speak Urdu or English at home (Pakistan Bureau of Statistics, 2017). The Balochistan Education Sector Analysis and Education Sector Plan 2020-2025 identifies language policy as the most problematic aspect of learning design, benefiting only a small urban minority (Government of Balochistan, 2019). Balochistan is renowned for its linguistic diversity, which is exemplified by the presence of numerous ethnic groups who speak various languages, such as Pashto, Balochi, and Brahui. Current language policy may tend to prioritize languages such as Urdu or English, which are frequently associated with urban areas and formal education. The language policy implemented in small urban areas may be aligned with the linguistic heritage and educational needs of the minority population, thereby facilitating their access to high-quality education. The implementation of this policy may

impede the education of the majority of Balochistan's students, particularly those from rural areas and from communities with diverse linguistic backgrounds.

Challenges and Opportunities in Implementing Mother/home Language Instruction and Contextualized Curriculum

Especially in resource-constrained contexts like Balochistan, implementing mother/home language instruction and contextualized curricula can be difficult and complex (Alidou et al., 2006; Benson & Kosonen, 2013). A lack of teaching materials in local languages, inadequate teacher training, resistance from parents and policymakers as discussed above, and opposition from parents and policymakers who may perceive the use of local languages as a threat to national unity or social mobility are among the most significant obstacles (Brock-Utne, 2000; Pinnock, 2009; Trudell, 2009). Moreover, there may be logistical challenges associated with the variety of languages spoken in a given region, necessitating careful planning and coordination to ensure that all students have access to instruction in their mother/home language (Ball, 2011; Heugh, 2011).

Limited literature explores the role of the medium of instruction in primary school educational outcomes, and the findings are mostly inconclusive. Several countries have shown that second language instruction leads to poorer performance compared to mother/home language instruction, including in Latvia, Hong Kong, Cameroon, Ghana, and other countries (Ivlevs & King, 2013; Yip, Tsang, & Cheung, 2003; Gfeller & Robinson, 1998; Collison, 1974; Bamgbose, 1991; Trudell, 2005; Mehrotra, 1998). Many of these studies were conducted on a limited number of classes, and as a result, the results may vary depending on class-specific factors. In addition, these studies, especially those from the literature on bilingual education, did not distinguish convincingly the effect of mother/home language instruction (on educational outcomes) from that of unobservable characteristics.

Implications for the Educational Context in Balochistan

The existing literature on mother/home language instruction and contextualized curricula provides valuable insights and direction for addressing the educational challenges confronting Balochistan. According to the Pakistan Reading Project (PRP) (2013) and the Annual Status of Education Report (ASER) (2018), the current language policy in Balochistan has contributed to subpar educational outcomes and high dropout rates among students. To enhance education quality, it is essential to reexamine the language policy and prioritize mother/home language instruction in early grades.

The purpose of this literature review is to comprehend the significance of contextualizing curriculum and promoting mother/home language instruction in early grades, with a particular focus on Balochistan, Pakistan. The government of Balochistan passed the "Introduction of Mother/home Languages as a Mandatory Additional Subject at Primary Level Act, 2014" to promote the use of mother/home languages in the educational system. This act intended to promote linguistic and cultural diversity in the province while also improving educational outcomes for students.

Balochistan continues to face obstacles in instituting mother/home language instruction and contextualizing the curriculum effectively despite the passage of this act. Numerous factors, including ineffective governance, political interference, and inadequate capacity within the education system, contribute to the learning crisis in the province (Benson & Kosonen, 2013; Hamid et al., 2010; Skutnabb-Kangas & Heugh, 2012). Existing curricula and textbooks in Pakistan generally fail to account for the unique context and linguistic diversity of Balochistan, impeding the education of many students in the province (Benson, 2002; Brock-Utne, 2000; Tollefson, 2008).

The training of teachers to equip them with skills in mother/home language instruction, preparation of learning materials, books, and other resources are crucial steps. In Balochistan, the recruitment policy requires teachers to belong to the same area where the schools exist; therefore, almost all teachers speak the mother/home language of the students, and the informal practice of using the mother/home language as a means of instruction continues. There is no teaching content/material or training program that builds on this advantage and prepares teachers using the mother/home language as a medium of instruction (Mathooko, M., 2009).

The Balochistan Introduction of Mother/home Languages as Compulsory Additional Subject at Primary Level Act, 2014, represents a significant step toward recognizing and enhancing the linguistic endowments of the province's students. Balochistan requires additional efforts to ensure the effective implementation of mother/home language instruction and contextualized curriculum. These efforts should include comprehensive assessments of current education policies and practices, as well as the development of targeted interventions to address the specific challenges facing the education system in the province (Collier, 2014; Skutnabb-Kangas & Heugh, 2012; UNESCO, 2008).

Literature on mother/home language instruction and contextualized curricula stress the importance of addressing language policy and curriculum design to improve educational outcomes in Balochistan. By adopting an approach to education that is more inclusive and sensitive to context, it is possible to improve the quality of education for all students and nurture the development of a more equitable and diverse society.

The review of literature focused on major themes and findings related to mother/home language instruction and contextualized curriculum. However, there are still gaps in Balochistan's research and endeavors in this field. This report aims to inspire more research and actions that improve educational performance in linguistically diverse situations by investigating the benefits and challenges of supporting mother/home language instruction and contextualized curriculum in the province.

4. Successful Initiatives and Case Studies

In the context of Balochistan, where research and practical implementation of mother/home language instruction and contextualized curriculum remain limited, a few notable initiatives and case studies have shown promise in improving educational outcomes.

1. Mother Language-based Multilingual Education (MLE) Pilot Project: Launched in 2012 by the Society for Community Support for Primary Education in Balochistan (SCSPEB), this project covered seven schools across the province. It aimed to boost educational achievements by providing instruction in students' mother/home language and a context-relevant curriculum during the early stages of education. According to the MLE project, students taught in their mother/home language exhibited superior academic performance compared to peers in conventional schools (UNESCO, 2016). The success of this pilot project underscores the potential of mother/home language instruction and contextualized curriculum to enhance learning outcomes.

Challenges: Limited resources, scaling beyond pilot schools, and resistance to change from traditional educational practices.

2. Mother Language-based Multilingual Education for Afghan Refugees: The International Rescue Committee (IRC) introduced this innovative project for Afghan refugee children in Balochistan. It provided instruction in Pashto, the children's native language, while gradually incorporating Urdu and English. The project's evaluation revealed significant improvements in learning outcomes, retention, and overall well-being (IRC, 2015). This project demonstrates how instruction in mother/home language and contextualized curriculum can benefit marginalized populations in Balochistan.

Challenges: Ensuring long-term sustainability, addressing language barriers and cultural disparities, and effective coordination with local authorities and communities.

3. The "Introduction of Mother Languages as Compulsory Additional Subject at Primary Level Act, 2014": Enacted by the Balochistan legislature, this legislation mandated the inclusion of mother languages as an additional subject at the primary level, recognizing the importance of mother tongue education in the region.

Challenges: Slow and uneven implementation, resistance to Urdu or English instruction, and limited resources for teacher training and curriculum development.

4. Language Supportive Teaching and Textbooks (LSTT) Project: Implemented by the British Council in Balochistan from 2015 to 2017, this project aimed to enhance education quality by providing language-supportive teaching materials and teacher training. It created culturally appropriate and linguistically comprehensible textbooks and equipped teachers to transition students from mother/home language to Urdu and English instruction. Despite challenges, the LSTT initiative led to improved student engagement, understanding, and academic achievement (British Council, 2017).

Challenges: Ensuring the quality of materials, expanding the project, and overcoming resistance to novel pedagogical approaches.

5. Strengthening Teacher Education in Pakistan (STEP) Program: The Institute for Educational Development at Agha Khan University has implemented the STEP Program in Balochistan. It focuses on enhancing teacher and teacher educator capacity to instruct in multilingual and multicultural contexts. The STEP program has shown positive results in terms of teacher efficacy and student academic achievement (AKU-IED, 2018).

Challenges: Securing continued funding, access to remote areas, and adoption by the School Education Department for scalability.

6. UNICEF-funded Accelerated Learning Program (ALP): This program, operational since 2016, provides supplementary education opportunities to children who are unable to attend primary school or have exceeded the age limit. The curriculum is tailored to Balochistan's unique needs, resulting in pass rates exceeding 95% according to the Balochistan Assessment and Examination Commission (BAEC). The ALP demonstrates the effectiveness of customized learning methods and contextualized curriculum for out-of-school children in Balochistan.

Challenges: Accessing remote communities, changing perceptions of out-of-school children, and ensuring sustainability and scalability.

These success stories highlight the potential benefits of implementing mother/home language instruction and contextualized curriculum to enhance educational achievements in Balochistan. While these initiatives have shown significant promise, further research and systematic implementation are essential to fully realize their potential and address the diverse challenges faced by Balochistan's education system.

5. Recommendations

The educational landscape in Balochistan stands at a critical juncture, demanding a concerted effort to address the challenges and seize the opportunities that lie ahead. Drawing from the review of the literature, it is evident that mother/home language instruction and curriculum contextualization hold immense promise for improving the educational outcomes of Balochistan's diverse student population. Nevertheless, these strategies face significant barriers that must be addressed to realize their full potential.

Literature resoundingly supports the importance of mother tongue instruction in the early grades (Seid, 2016). Numerous studies have shown that children who learn in their mother tongue perform significantly better academically, experience lower dropout rates, and exhibit higher self-esteem (Seid, 2016). The cognitive and linguistic advantages of this approach are well-documented, making a strong case for its adoption in Balochistan. Moreover, it aligns with the Balochistan Introduction of Mother Languages as Compulsory Additional Subject at Primary Level Act, 2014. Nonetheless, there is an imperative need for thoughtful consideration and robust policy backing to implement mother/home language instruction in the early grades. This entails a thorough review and potential amendment of the existing Act, along with the establishment of comprehensive rules and regulations

governing its application. Additionally, it necessitates assigning expanded responsibilities to each affiliated organization within the Balochistan secondary school department. A crucial component of this endeavor would involve developing a well-defined five-year implementation plan for the gradual integration of mother/home language instruction in the early grades.

Contextualized curriculum and pedagogical techniques are essential for ensuring the relevance and efficacy of education in Balochistan. The literature highlights the need for teachers to be familiar with subject matter, employ the language of instruction effectively, and have access to instructional materials (Moats, L. 2009). It is imperative to shift towards prioritizing learners' self-expression and critical thinking skills, fostering a more innovative and inclusive approach to teaching.

Existing programs frequently overlook the challenges of multigrade teaching and do not equip teachers with the skills necessary to implement mother tongue instruction effectively. As Mulryan-Kyne, C. (2007) stresses upon proper and relevant preparation of teacher is essential in a comprehensive evaluation and restructuring of teacher education programs. Judicious and moderate use of mother/home language as language of instruction does not hinder learning; rather, it assists, aids and facilitates the teaching and learning process thus providing the teacher with an effective pedagogical tool for maximizing the learning outcomes. (Shuchi, I., & Islam, A. 2016)

Another good example is the study in Singapore where English teachers believe in an immersion approach but also believe that mother/home language can aid in learning English, and the more experienced the teacher, the more likely they are to believe in the use of mother/home language, suggesting implications for teacher education programs (Vaish, V. 2012). The sporadic in-service teacher education programs should be replaced with consistent, high-quality offerings. These programs should address the changing requirements of educators considering curriculum and pedagogical modifications.

The incorporation of local cultural material in teaching material developed for the students. Teaching material plays an important part in the teaching learning process, yet inappropriate teaching materials may become more harmful than useful. The study on Language awareness by (Byram, M. 2012) found that the use of culturally familiar materials is beneficial for the students learning process. The result of the study also highlighted students' needs and prior knowledge as the main factors to be considered when developing teaching material. New teaching and learning materials should be developed after extensive research and consultation with relevant stakeholders. These materials should be culturally relevant, linguistically acceptable, and supportive of the educational requirements of Balochistan's students. Bottom of Form

Teachers require ongoing academic and pedagogical support to effectively implement curriculum modifications. In this regard, the Ladson-Billings Culturally Relevant Pedagogy (CRP) framework can be a valuable resource, assisting teachers in adapting their methods to meet the diverse requirements of their students.

The revision of the teacher recruitment policy emerges as a pivotal area for development. It is imperative that this policy places a primary focus on preservice education components that are in alignment with the contextualized curriculum and instructional methods. Furthermore, there should be a phased approach to implementing in-service training for teachers already within the education system, ensuring that they acquire the requisite skills and knowledge.

Language policy wields considerable influence over educational opportunities and outcomes. Historically, policies in Pakistan have exhibited a bias in favor of dominant languages like Urdu and English, often overlooking the indigenous languages spoken by the majority in Balochistan. This historical trend has led to subpar educational outcomes and elevated dropout rates among children. An analysis of English-medium education policy in Pakistan, as evidenced in the study by (Manan, David, and Dumanig 2015), underscores that English is often foreign to the sociocultural ecologies of most children, resulting in a range of disadvantages, including difficulty comprehending subject material, a reliance on rote learning, diminished creativity and critical thinking, and decreased parental engagement in the teaching and learning processes. To rectify this situation, it is imperative to reconsider and reprioritize language policy, with a renewed emphasis on mother/home language instruction. This realignment aligns harmoniously with the findings derived from the existing body of literature and addresses the linguistic diversity inherent to the province. Notably, an ongoing study seeks to provide empirical findings that could significantly contribute to the formulation of an informed and effective School Language policy, representing a pioneering effort in Balochistan.

Parental involvement in the educational process yields substantial benefits, including lower school dropout rates, increased on-time high school completion, and higher levels of educational attainment (Barnard, 2004; Hashmi & Akhter, 2013). Challenges stemming from historical, colonial, and post-Zia eras have manifested as obstacles within Pakistan's education system, particularly regarding the use of mother/home language as the medium of instruction. A study conducted in Nigeria (Iyamu, E., & Ogiegbaen, S. 2007). has indicated that both parents and teachers value mother-tongue education; however, parents often express hesitation when it comes to having their children instructed in their native language. Primary impediments to implementing mother/home language instruction include the advocacy for more widely spoken languages and the scarcity of suitable teaching materials. Given the undeniable significance of mother/home language education, fostering engagement with local communities, parents, and other stakeholders becomes paramount in raising awareness about the importance of mother/home language instruction. This underscores the necessity for community-oriented activities (Iyamu, E., & Ogiegbaen, S. 2007).

6. Challenges and Opportunities

The endeavor to implement mother tongue instruction and contextualized curriculum in resource-constrained contexts like Balochistan brings forth a unique set of challenges, including limited access to teaching materials, inadequately trained teachers, and resistance from various stakeholders.

Notably, significant opposition to change may emanate from religious political parties and influential factions within the government establishment. Given the prevailing insurgency and the proximity of the Taliban government, it is plausible that voices within these circles may resist the integration of mother/home language instruction into early education, as it ideally should. This resistance is predicated on the belief that such a transition may exacerbate the detachment of the province from a unified national identity, and it is also perceived as potentially undermining the Islamic education of children, which is currently supported by the existing curriculum. Addressing this formidable challenge necessitates the initiation of comprehensive research. Armed with empirical evidence, advocates can embark on higher-level advocacy efforts, engaging the appropriate channels to demonstrate that introducing education in the mother/home language not only enhances learning outcomes but also fosters unity and peaceful coexistence. Furthermore, it facilitates the seamless continuation of Islamic education in the mother/home language, akin to what transpires in Urdu or English, potentially deepening students' understanding (Manan, David, & Dumanig, 2017).

Resource limitations pose a significant obstacle to the initiative in Balochistan, aimed at adopting the mother tongue as the language of instruction and contextualizing the curriculum. Current educational budgets may prove insufficient, potentially constraining opportunities for program expansion and innovation. Budgets may already be stretched to their limits due to the existing financial commitments related to ongoing educational operations and salaries. Furthermore, funding priorities may skew towards other pressing challenges, leaving minimal financial flexibility for projects such as mother/home language instruction and curriculum contextualization. Inadequate infrastructure may also necessitate a substantial initial investment to create a conducive environment for this new form of instruction. Moreover, a dearth of pre-existing instructional content in the mother/home language necessitates the creation, translation, and distribution of new learning resources.

Addressing these resource constraints requires a concerted effort to secure additional funding. Various avenues can be explored to obtain the necessary financial resources. One potential approach is to advocate for increased governmental budget allocations for education, with a specific focus on linguistic and cultural contextualization of the curriculum. Seeking assistance or subsidies from international educational organizations, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), or countries with vested interests in promoting linguistic and cultural diversity represents another viable option. Public-private partnerships can be established to garner support and share resources, further enriching the financial and operational landscape. Engaging the local community to contribute resources, whether in the form of physical assets, spaces, or volunteer services, may also offer financial relief. Initiatives like crowdfunding campaigns and soliciting donations from individuals and groups passionate about advancing mother/home language education and cultural preservation can serve as potential sources of funding. Lastly, exploring research grants that focus on linguistic, cultural, or educational advancements could provide a means to secure the necessary financial backing. By addressing these resource constraints effectively, the initiative to integrate the mother tongue as the language of instruction and contextualize the curriculum in Balochistan can progress towards realization.

A glaring issue is the current dearth of research in Balochistan, underscoring the imperative need for a thorough examination of the educational landscape. Research stands as a crucial tool for comprehending the current state of education, evaluating the effectiveness of the prevailing language of instruction, and assessing the level of acceptance among stakeholders concerning a transition to mother/home language instruction. Additionally, localized research is indispensable to obtain specific insights into how such a transition could enhance educational outcomes in Balochistan. Furthermore, research can facilitate the customization of the curriculum to ensure linguistic and cultural relevance, effectively addressing the unique needs and preferences of the local population. Anticipating and navigating challenges becomes a more streamlined process with comprehensive research, as it can provide valuable data on potential hurdles and suggest strategies to overcome them. Additionally, research enables accurate cost estimation, pivotal for budgeting and fundraising. It can significantly influence policy formulation, providing compelling evidence to education authorities and policymakers regarding the benefits of mother tongue instruction.

Upon the implementation of the initiative, ongoing research plays a vital role in measuring the impact of mother/home language instruction on student learning outcomes. This, in turn, guides future policy and strategy decisions. The methodology for conducting such research is multifaceted and could encompass a thorough review of existing literature on mother/home language instruction at both global and local levels. Surveys and questionnaires distributed among various stakeholders, such as educators, parents, and students, can help gather opinions and insights. Focus group discussions within communities provide a deeper understanding of attitudes and concerns regarding mother tongue instruction. The examination of case studies from socio-cultural or geopolitical settings akin to Balochistan, where mother/home language instruction has been successfully implemented, can offer valuable lessons. The conduct of baseline educational assessments to gauge current learning levels, as well as ongoing assessments to evaluate the impact of mother/home language instruction, is crucial.

Detailed cost analysis can provide an estimate of the financial resources required for this transition, while policy analysis can identify gaps and opportunities in existing educational policies. Collaborations with educational institutions, government bodies, and NGOs can facilitate support, knowledge sharing, and resource pooling. By embarking on a systematic research approach, particularly considering the limited existing research in Balochistan, stakeholders can attain a holistic understanding of the various dimensions involved in transitioning to mother/home language instruction, thus ensuring informed decision-making and effective implementation of this pivotal educational initiative.

7. Conclusion

The linguistic and cultural fabric of Balochistan is as diverse as it is rich. It stands as a realm where ancient tongues narrate the tales of distinct tribes and communities, each carrying its own unique heritage and knowledge. However, the province's educational framework has yet to fully embrace this linguistic diversity, especially in the realm of early education. This research embarked on a critical expedition to scrutinize the prospects of

integrating mother/home language instruction within the primary educational landscape of Balochistan, a journey led by the quintessence of linguistic equity and cultural recognition.

The exploration was not without its challenges. As elucidated in the introductory segments, the endeavor to align the education system closer to the cultural and linguistic roots of the Balochistan populace faces substantial resistance. The stronghold of religious political parties and the government establishment, coupled with the looming shadows of insurgency and the Taliban's proximity, presents a formidable obstacle. Furthermore, there is a tangible fear of estranging the province from a unified national identity and perceived threats to the Islamic educational fabric. This research argues that such fears, while valid, may stem from a lack of comprehensive understanding and engagement with the complex interplay of language, identity, and education.

During this journey, a thorough exploration of the manifold dimensions encompassing the initiative was undertaken, ranging from policy advocacy to resource mobilization, and from community engagement to pedagogical transitions. A substantive part of this inquiry was dedicated to dissecting the financial contours of introducing mother/home language instruction. It became glaringly evident that without robust financial scaffolding, the ambition to nurture the roots of native languages within the classrooms could remain an elusive dream. The narrative further unfolded the multifaceted avenues through which financial resources could be mobilized, setting a pragmatic tone on how the fiscal aspect of this initiative could be approached.

A stark revelation from this investigation is the dire need for localized research. The existing scholarly landscape is largely barren of substantial empirical studies focusing on Balochistan's educational dynamics, more so concerning mother/home language instruction. The discourse stressed the pivotal role that meticulous research would play not only in understanding the existing landscape but also in crafting strategies that resonate with the local socio-cultural and political tapestry.

It's imperative to acknowledge the essence of community engagement and proactive dialogue among stakeholders. The aspiration to revitalize native languages within the educational discourse should not be seen as an isolated academic endeavor, but as a collective journey towards linguistic inclusivity and cultural appreciation. The notion of initiating pilot programs came forth as a pragmatic step to manifest the envisioned transition, coupled with a robust framework for monitoring, evaluating, and continually refining the approach based on real-world data and feedback.

The advocacy for mother/home language instruction is not a call for linguistic seclusion, but a plea for linguistic and cultural inclusivity. It's a pursuit for an educational ecosystem where the rich linguistic heritage of Balochistan is celebrated and nurtured, and where the seeds of curiosity and knowledge are sown in the fertile grounds of native tongues. The endeavor is to create a milieu where the Islamic ethos and national unity are not seen as being at loggerheads with linguistic diversity, but rather as harmonious threads in a beautifully diverse tapestry.

In forging ahead, it becomes imperative to create a harmonized nexus of policymakers, educators, communities, and financial stakeholders, united by a shared vision of fostering a linguistically equitable and culturally vibrant educational landscape in Balochistan. The roadmap laid down in this paper, punctuated with practical recommendations and insights, serves as a foundation upon which this significant educational transition can be envisaged and actualized.

As this inquiry draws to a close, it leaves behind a trail of thoughts, a compendium of actionable strategies, and a clarion call for embracing the linguistic and cultural essence of Balochistan within its educational sanctum. The narrative penned down herein is a modest contribution towards a discourse that seeks not merely to educate but to enlighten, not merely to instruct but to inspire, and not merely to comply but to celebrate the kaleidoscopic linguistic and cultural milieu that is Balochistan.

8. References

1. Aga Khan University's Institute for Educational Development (AKU-IED). (2018). *Strengthening Teacher Education in Pakistan (STEP)*. Karachi: AKU-IED.
2. Ahmad, I. (2004). *Islam, Democracy and Citizenship Education: An Examination of the Social Studies Curriculum in Pakistan*. *Current Issues in Comparative Education*.
3. Ahmed, M., & Baloch, A. (2015). *POLITICAL ECONOMY OF BALOCHISTAN, PAKISTAN: A CRITICAL REVIEW*. *European Scientific Journal, ESJ*, 11.
4. ASER Pakistan. (2018). *Annual Status of Education Report (ASER)*.
5. Asif, S., Afzal, I., & Bashir, R. (2020). *An Analysis of Medium of Instruction Policies in the Education System of Pakistan with Specific Reference to English Medium Education*. [DOI]
6. Ball, J. (2011). *Enhancing learning of children from diverse language backgrounds: Mother/home tongue-based bilingual or multilingual education in the early years*. UNESCO.
7. Balochistan Provincial Assembly. (2014). *The Balochistan Introduction of Mother Languages as Compulsory Additional Subject at Primary Level Act, 2014*. Quetta: Balochistan Provincial Assembly.
8. Bamgbose, A. (1991). *Language and the nation: The language question in sub-Saharan Africa*. Edinburgh University Press.
9. Barnard, W. (2004). *Parent involvement in elementary school and educational attainment*. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 26, 39-62. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CHILDYOUTH.2003.11.002>
10. Benson, C. (2002). *Indigenous language medium education in Nigeria: From policy to implementation*. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 22(5), 481-494.
11. Benson, C., & Kosonen, K. (2013). *Mother/home tongue-based multilingual education: A study of the Breadth and Depth of current practice in Asia*. UNESCO.
12. British Council. (2017). *Language Supportive Teaching and Textbooks in Tanzania and Pakistan: An Evaluation*. London: British Council.
13. Byram, M. (2012). *Language awareness and (critical) cultural awareness – relationships, comparisons and contrasts*. *Language Awareness*, 21, 13 <https://doi.org/10.1080/09658416.2011.639887>.
14. Collier, V. P. (2014). *Dual language education for a transformed world*. *International Multilingual Research Journal*, 8(1), 30-45.
15. Cummins, J. (2000). *Language, power, and pedagogy: Bilingual children in the crossfire*. *Multilingual Matters*.
16. Dahm, R., & Angelis, G. (2018). *The role of mother/home tongue literacy in language*

- learning and mathematical learning: Is there a multilingual benefit for both?. *International Journal of Multilingualism*, 15, 194-213.
17. Government of Balochistan. (n.d.). Balochistan. [emis.gob.pk].
 18. Hamid, M. O., Baldauf Jr, R. B., & Lin, W. (2010). *Medium of instruction in Asia: Contexts, outcomes, and policy implications*. Routledge.
 19. Hantzopoulos, M. (2011). Institutionalizing critical peace education in public schools: A case for comprehensive implementation. *Journal of Peace Education*, 8, 225 - 242. [DOI]
 20. Hashmi, A., & Akhter., M. (2013). Assessing the Parental Involvement in Schooling of Children in Public /Private Schools, and Its Impact on Their Achievement at Elementary Level. *Journal of Educational Research*, 16, 27.
 21. Heugh, K. (2011). Multilingual education for South Africa: A discussion of the evidence. *Reading & Writing*, 2(1), 1-24.
 22. Imran, M. (2018). Disempowered, Disenfranchised and Disengaged: Balochistan in Focus Name. , 91-102. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-97076-9_7. (
 23. International Rescue Committee (IRC). (2015). *Learning in a Mother Tongue: A Case Study of Mother Language-based Multilingual Education for Afghan Refugee Children in Pakistan*. New York: International Rescue Committee.
 24. Ivlevs, A., & King, R. (2013). Economic returns to English-language skills in the export labor market: Evidence from India. *Economic Development and Cultural Change*, 61(2), 333-365.
 25. Iyamu, E., & Ogiegbaen, S. (2007). Parents and Teachers' Perceptions of Mother-Tongue Medium of Instruction Policy in Nigerian Primary Schools. *Language, Culture and Curriculum*, 20, 108 - 97. <https://doi.org/10.2167/lcc328.0>.
 26. Jamal, H., & Iqbal, M. A. (2021). *Educational Status of Pakistan: Pre and Post 18th Amendment Scenario*.
 27. Khan, G., & Ahmed, M. (2022). *Balochistan: Its History, Geopolitics and Conflict*.
 28. Manan, S., David, M., & Dumanig, F. (2015). Disjunction between language policy and children's sociocultural ecology – an analysis of English-medium education policy in Pakistan. *Language and Education*, 29, 453 - 473. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09500782.2015.1046882>.
 29. Manan, S., David, M., & Dumanig, F. (2017). Ethnolinguistic dilemma and static maintenance syndrome: A study of language policies and language perceptions in Pakistan. *Language Problems and Language Planning*, 41, 66-86. <https://doi.org/10.1075/LPLP.41.1.04MAN>
 30. Mathooko, M. (2009). Actualizing Free Primary Education in Kenya for Sustainable Development. *The Journal of Pan-African Studies*, 2, 151.
 31. Mehfooz, M. (2021). Religious Freedom in Pakistan: A Case Study of Religious Minorities. *Religion*, 12, 51. <https://doi.org/10.3390/REL12010051>.
 32. Mehrotra, S. (1998). Language policy and instruction in India. *Journal of Language, Identity & Education*, 8(3-4), 295-312.
 33. Mulryan-Kyne, C. (2007). The preparation of teachers for multigrade teaching. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 23, 501-514. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.TATE.2006.12.003>
 34. Nishanthi, R. (2020). Understanding of the Importance of Mother Tongue Learning. *International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development*.
 35. Pakistan Reading Programme. (2013). *Pakistan Reading Project (PRP)*. [Report].
 36. Qasim, A., & Qasim, Z. (2014). The Role of language in Education: An Analytical Review of Pakistan's Education Policy 2009. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 5, 159-164.
 37. Ramsey, S. (2017). *Balochistan In quest of Freedom by Syed Ramsey*.
 38. Samad, Y. (2014). Understanding the insurgency in Balochistan. *Commonwealth & Comparative Politics*, 52, 293 - 320. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14662043.2014.894280>.
 39. Seid, Y. (2016). Does learning in mother/home tongue matter? Evidence from a natural experiment in Ethiopia. *Economics of Education Review*, 55, 21-38. [DOI]
 40. Seid, Y. (2018). The impact of learning first in mother/home tongue: evidence from a natural experiment in Ethiopia. *Applied Economics*, 51, 577-593.

41. Shuchi, I., & Islam, A. (2016). Teachers' and Students' Attitudes towards L1 Use in EFL Classrooms in the Contexts of Bangladesh and Saudi Arabia.. *English Language Teaching*, 9, 62- 73. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ELT.V9N12P62>.
42. Skutnabb-Kangas, T. (2000). *Linguistic genocide in education—or worldwide diversity and human rights?* Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
43. Syed, S., Saeed, L., & Martin, R. (2015). Causes and Incentives for Terrorism in Pakistan. *Journal of Tollefson, J. W.* (2008). *Language policies in education: Critical issues.* Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
44. Stoicovy, C. (2002). A Case for Culturally Responsive Pedagogy. *International Research in Geographical and Environmental Education*, 11, 80 - 84. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10382040208667470>
45. Trudell, B., & Piper, B. (2014). Whatever the law says: language policy implementation and early-grade literacy achievement in Kenya. *Current Issues in Language Planning*. [DOI]
46. UNESCO. (2008). *Education for all global monitoring report 2009: Overcoming inequality: Why governance matters.* UNESCO.
47. UNESCO. (2016). *Education for People and Planet: Creating Sustainable Futures for All. Global Education Monitoring Report 2016.* Paris: UNESCO.
48. UNICEF Pakistan. (n.d.). *Accelerated Learning Program.* Retrieved from <https://www.unicef.org/pakistan/education>
49. Vaish, V. (2012). Teacher beliefs regarding bilingualism in an English medium reading program. *International Journal of Bilingual Education and Bilingualism*, 15, 53 - 69. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13670050.2011.594496>.
50. Yazici, Z., Ilter, B., & Glover, P. (2010). How bilingual is bilingual? Mother-tongue proficiency and learning through a second language. *International Journal of Early Years Education*, 18, 259 - 268.
51. Yip, P. S., Tsang, P. Y., & Cheung, K. S. (2003). Introduction: medium of instruction policies in Asia. In *Language policy and education in multilingual societies* (pp. 1-12). Springer.

Author Note

The content presented in this paper reflects the author's personal views and does not bear any direct or indirect affiliation with the author's employing organization. The views articulated herein draw primarily from the author's extensive experience, spanning over two decades, within the education sector of Balochistan.